

The Norwegian Seamen's Church in Cardiff

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The Norwegian Seamen's Church was the fourth Norwegian mission church abroad, with the first three being in Leith (Edinburgh), North Shields (Newcastle), and Antwerp. The Norwegian Seamen's Mission began its activity in 1864, and the church in Cardiff started its activity two years later in 1866, with the church building being ready in 1868 and consecrated a year later. The church was immensely popular with Norwegians arriving in the port in Cardiff, at the time the world's largest coal exporting port. Norwegians came with timber for the pit props in the coal mines and brought coal to the world. Activity declined following World War II, and the Norwegian Seamen's Mission left the church in Cardiff in 1959. However, it continued to be used by the Norwegian community and the World Lutheran Federation until 1974. The building was dismantled in 1989 and resurrected at its current location as an arts centre in 1992; it is still used for this purpose today.

Date Range: 1866 CE - 1959 CE

Region: The Norwegian Seamen's Church in Cardiff

Region tags: Wales

The two locations where the Norwegian Seamen's Church building has been located in Cardiff.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Roese, Herbert. "Cardiff's Norwegian Heritage: A Neglected Theme", *Welsh-History Review/Cylchgrawn Hanes Cymru*, 18.2, 1996, 255-271.
- Source 2: Persen, Peter. *The Norwegian Seamen's Church Cardiff Bay, Cardiff*: Seeprint Limited, 2013.
- Source 3: Aarseth, Ivar and Brunn, C. *Den Norske Sjomandsmission i Bristolkanalens Havne, 1866-1916, Cardiff*: South Wales Printing and Publishing Company, 1916.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://archives.wales/2019/12/10/the-norwegian-church-cardiff/>
- Source 1 Description: Glamorgan Archivist Susan Edwards article on the Norwegian Church in Cardiff Bay
- Source 2 URL: <https://archwilio.org.uk/her/chi3/arch.php?county=Glamorgan%20Gwent%20Archaeological%20Trust=&lang=eng>
- Source 2 Description: Archwilio open access GIS of the Historical Environment of South Wales, this record includes the Norwegian Church in Cardiff
- Source 3 URL: <https://cadwpublic-api.azurewebsites.net/reports/listedbuilding/FullReport?lang=&id=87910>
- Source 3 Description: Cadw full listed building report from when the building was listed in 2023

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Other [specify]: N/A - but it is associated with the built landscape of Cardiff Bay and is an important part of the history and heritage of this once busy industrial port

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The church is located on the shore in Cardiff Bay.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: It is shaped as a Norwegian village church, with a big church hall making up the nave.

↳ One single feature

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

Notes: But it was a part of larger global Norwegian Lutheran movement which funded churches across the world, there were three other churches in Wales (Barry, Newport, and Swansea), approximately thirty in the UK, and over one hundred globally. They are still active today, but the Cardiff church is now an arts centre.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

- ↳ Worship:
 - Communal

– Worship

- ↳ Worship:
 - Individual

– Social

Notes: In addition to being a place of worship it was also a social hub for Norwegians in Cardiff and South Wales, with a library, common room, and activities organised.

– Political

Notes: Norwegian Seamen's Churches was also a place to emphasis Norwegian identity and politics among sailors

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
 - Yes

Notes: The church was expanded several times such as in 1882, 1888, and 1894 due to the many Norwegians arriving in the port. The church was originally built in corrugated iron so that it would be easy to move, this was changed in 1884 when it was clad in wood. The church building was also demolished in 1989, and resurrected in 1992 with a slightly different interior to meet its new purpose as an arts centre.

- ↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
 - No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

- ↳ In modernity
 - Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: God

Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Priests

– Men

– Women

– Other [specify]: Norwegian sailors

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Notes: The Norwegian Seamen's Mission started their activity in Cardiff due to the trade between Norway and this important industrial port.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– No

Notes: Money for the building was risen by the Norwegian Seamen's Mission, and the church was built on land provided by the Marquess of Bute.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: N/A

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Earth

– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– No

↳ Plaster
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– No

Notes: The current wood comes cladding the building comes from western Norway.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– No

↳ Other
–Other [specify]: N/A

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

–Yes [specify]: Wooden planks

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: Stained glass windows and model of ship, which was a common decorative feature in Norwegian Seamen's Mission Churches.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– No

↳ Floral motifs

– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Stained glass windows and ship model

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:
– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:
– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)
– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)
– Yes

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:
– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– No

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: N/A

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: N/A

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: With the one god of Christianity through prayer.

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Traditional Christian rituals such as baptisms, weddings, and funerals.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
– specify: N/A

↳ How often do these rituals take place:
– specify: N/A

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:
– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:
– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:
– No

Are material offerings present:
– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:
– Yes

↳ By all the community
– Yes

↳ By specific individuals

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: Maintenance was carried out by the Assistant at the Cardiff Church

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: But most of the visitors would have come from trading vessels from Norway.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

–specify: All the traditional annual Christian festivals, plus annual Norwegian cultural festivals

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: Number is impossible to estimate as it was changing depending on activity in the ports of Cardiff Bay.

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Elites

– Non-elites

– Religious professionals

Notes: All who attended the feasts at festivals such as Christmas and Easter in the church.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

Notes: There was permanent Pastor located at the church every year until it closed as a Seamen's Church in 1959.

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: At the time they were all male priests.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Notes: All the Pastors from the beginning in 1866 to the church closed as a Seamen's Church in 1959 was Norwegians.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Notes: The Pastor at the church had his own accommodation on Cathedral Road in Cardiff.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– No

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– No

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: It served as a post office for sending letters and parcels between Norway and Cardiff, as well as a bank during World War II, lending money to Norwegian sailors and refugees who needed it.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: Amongst other things the church had a library with reading material for visitors who wished to read Norwegian newspapers, books, etc.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The Norwegian Seamen's Church in Cardiff, Roese, Herbert. "Cardiff's Norwegian Heritage: A Neglected Theme". *Welsh-history Review/cylchgrawn Hanes Cymru* 18, no. 2 (1996): 255-71.

Reference: The Norwegian Seamen's Church in Cardiff, Persen, Per. *The Norwegian Seamen's Church Cardiff Bay*. Cardiff: Seeprint Limited, 2013.

Reference: The Norwegian Seamen's Church in Cardiff, Aarseth, Ivar, and Christian Bruun. *Den Norske Sjomandsmission I Bristolkanalens Havne, 1866-1916*. Cardiff: South Wales Printing and Publishing Company, 1916.

Reference: The Norwegian Seamen's Church in Cardiff, Williams, David . *Mymryn O Norwy Yng Nghymru: Atgofion Am Yr Eglwysi Morwyr Norwyaidd/a Little Piece of Norway in Wales: Recollections of the Norwegian Seamen's Churches/en Lite Stykke Norge I Wales: Minner Fra De Norske Sjømannskirkene*. Edited by Karen Allen and Wenche Davies. Cardiff: Norwegian Church Cultural Centre, 2006.

Reference: The Norwegian Seamen's Church in Cardiff, Hanson, Johanne Elster. "En Liten Norsk Juvel". *Vagant* 1 (2022). <https://www.vagant.no/en-liten-norsk-juvel-roald-dahl/>.

Reference: The Norwegian Seamen's Church in Cardiff, Hoel, Virginia. *Faith, Fatherland and the Norwegian Seaman : The Work of the Norwegian Seamen's Mission in Antwerp and the Dutch Ports (1864-1920)*. Hilversum: Verloren, 2016.

Reference: The Norwegian Seamen's Church in Cardiff, Edwards, Susan . "The Norwegian Church, Cardiff", 2019. <https://archives.wales/2019/12/10/the-norwegian-church-cardiff/>.

Reference: The Norwegian Seamen's Church in Cardiff, Husøy, Thomas Alexander. "Exploring the Past: Uncovering the Story of the Norwegian Church". Edited by Thomas Alexander Husøy and Olivia Ciaccia. Digital Historical Exhibition, 2023. <https://view.genial.ly/647512459a329e00189df3ce/interactive-content->

online-exhibition.